

ACADEMIC SELF-CONCEPT AS A PREDICTOR OF LEARNING OUTCOMES OF THE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this study was to determine whether academic self-concept serves as a predictor of learning outcomes among Grade 12 students in the District of Carmen, Bohol, for the Academic Year 2022-2023. Specifically, the study aimed to assess the level of academic self-concept in terms of academic effort and confidence, as well as the level of learning outcomes across the naturalistic, musical, logical, existential, interpersonal, kinesthetic, verbal, intrapersonal, and visual domains. Additionally, it sought to identify which domains of learning outcomes have a significant relationship with academic self-concept and whether academic self-concept predicts learning outcomes. A descriptive-quantitative research design was employed, and data were analyzed using statistical methods, including weighted mean, Pearson's correlation coefficient (Pearson-r), and multiple linear regression analysis. The findings revealed that students exhibited a high level of academic effort and academic confidence. In terms of learning outcomes, they demonstrated high levels in the existential and intrapersonal domains, while their naturalistic, musical, logical, interpersonal, kinesthetic, verbal, and visual learning outcomes were at a moderate level. Furthermore, the results indicated that students' naturalistic, logical, existential, interpersonal, kinesthetic, intrapersonal, and visual learning outcomes had a significant relationship with their academic self-concept, suggesting that these domains are influenced by academic self-concept. Conversely, no significant relationship was found between the musical and verbal learning outcomes and academic self-concept, indicating that these domains are not affected by students' academic self-perception. Moreover, the study concluded that academic self-concept

does not serve as a predictor of students' learning outcomes. Based on these findings, it is recommended that the guidance counselor implement academic self-concept enhancement programs, psycho-educational interventions, and counseling sessions to support students' academic and personal development.

Keywords: *academic self-concept, confidence, learning outcomes, multiple intelligences, predictor, and student motivation*

INTRODUCTION

Self-concept is a fundamental component of human personality, encompassing an individual's perception of their physical, social, and academic competence. It is a construct that reflects a person's self-awareness, attributes, qualities, values, and relationships (Zahra et al., 2010). One of the significant dimensions of self-concept is academic self-concept (ASC), which refers to an individual's personal beliefs about their academic abilities or skills (Benner & Mistry, 2007). It is shaped early in life by parenting styles and educational experiences and continues to develop throughout academic and social engagements (Marsh & Martin, 2011).

Academic self-concept has been widely studied in psychology and education due to its influence on academic performance, effort, engagement, and persistence in learning activities (Bong & Skaalvik, 2003). Many theories and models have attempted to explain the relationship between academic self-concept and academic achievement. However, there is still no conclusive evidence proving whether a higher level of academic self-awareness leads to improved academic performance or if better academic grades enhance academic self-concept.

Academic achievement or performance is the outcome of education, reflecting students' ability to attain learning goals. While academic self-concept influences academic success, it also affects students' motivation, effort, and course selection (Ahmavaara & Houston, 2007). Some researchers have examined the correlation between academic self-concept and academic performance, but studies specifically focusing on its relationship with learning outcomes remain limited. This gap in research highlights the need to explore whether academic self-concept can be a predictor of students' learning outcomes.

The theoretical foundation of this study is grounded in Baller's (1968) Maturation Theory, which posits that self-concept significantly influences learning outcomes. The theory emphasizes that while social and cultural environments play roles in students' development, internal self-concept remains a critical determinant. Additionally, the Self-Worth Theory (Covington, 2000) asserts that individuals strive to maintain a positive self-image, affecting their academic motivation and engagement. Furthermore, Shavelson's Hierarchical Model of Self-Concept (1976) suggests that academic self-concept is domain-specific and directly impacts performance in different academic subjects.

Several empirical studies support the notion that academic self-concept is intricately linked to academic performance. Guay et al. (2010) found that students with higher academic self-concept demonstrated greater autonomy and motivation, leading to better grades. Similarly, research by Marsh and Craven (2006) provided evidence that a strong academic self-concept contributes to higher academic achievement. Other scholars, such as Green et al. (2006) and Liu (2010), emphasize the importance of investigating self-concept due to its potential impact on students' future aspirations and overall academic success.

Learning outcomes, defined as the measurable knowledge, skills, abilities, and attitudes acquired through education (Adam, 2006), serve as a critical measure of students' academic progress. Howard Gardner's (1985) Multiple Intelligences Theory suggests that students learn in different ways, highlighting the need for educators to consider diverse learning styles to optimize learning outcomes. These learning outcomes can be categorized into multiple domains, including naturalistic, musical, logical, existential, interpersonal, kinesthetic, verbal, intrapersonal, and visual intelligence.

In alignment with the Department of Education's (DepEd) research agenda (DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2016), this study aims to assess the factors influencing student learning outcomes by examining the role of academic self-concept. The study will specifically investigate whether academic self-concept, as measured by academic effort and academic confidence (Liu & Wang, 2005), is a significant predictor of students' learning outcomes across different intelligence domains.

Thus, this research seeks to fill the gap in literature by determining the relationship between academic self-concept and learning outcomes among Grade 12 students in the District of Carmen, Bohol, for the Academic Year 2022-2023. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights into how self-perception impacts educational attainment and inform educators, policymakers, and stakeholders in developing strategies to enhance students' academic experiences.

Research Questions

The study purposely delved into determining if academic self-concept was a predictor of the learning outcomes of the Grade 12 students in the District of Carmen, Bohol, Academic Year 2022-2023.

It specifically sought answers to the following:

1. What is the level of academic self-concept of the students in terms of:
 - 1.1 academic effort, and
 - 1.2 academic confidence?
2. What is the level of students' learning outcomes in terms of the following domains:
 - 2.1 naturalistic,
 - 2.2 musical,
 - 2.3 logical,

- 2.4 existential,
 - 2.5 interpersonal,
 - 2.6 kinesthetic,
 - 2.7 verbal,
 - 2.8 intrapersonal, and
 - 2.9 visual?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of academic self-concept and the level of learning outcomes of students in terms of the following domains:
 - 3.1 naturalistic;
 - 3.2 musical;
 - 3.3 logical;
 - 3.4 existential;
 - 3.5 interpersonal;
 - 3.6 kinesthetic;
 - 3.7 verbal;
 - 3.8 intrapersonal; and
 - 3.9 visual?
 4. Is academic self-concept a predictor of the learning outcomes?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed the descriptive design wherein the quantitative data were gathered. The survey questionnaire was utilized to measure the level of academic self-concept and the level of learning outcomes of the students.

Research Environment and Participants

The study was conducted in the district of Carmen, one of the five districts within the 3rd Congressional District of the Division of Bohol, alongside Bilar, Batuan, Sierra Bullones, and Pilar (BIBACASIPI). Carmen was selected due to the restrictions imposed during the COVID-19 pandemic, which limited the researcher's ability to travel and distribute research questionnaires to multiple locations. Consequently, the study focused on public secondary schools within Carmen for more feasible data collection. Historically, Carmen was part of the municipality of Bilar and was originally called Imbaya, named after a local brook. It later became an independent municipality and was renamed in honor of a prominent local figure. The district consists of 29 barangays and houses nine public high schools: Pedro S. Budiongan High School, Katipunan National High School, Isabel Gujol High School, Francisco L. Adlaon High School, Policronio S. Dano Sr. High School, Vallehermoso High School, Ponciano F. Ramasola High School, Ambassador Pablo S. Suarez High School, and Valeriano Ganas High School.

To ensure the clarity, validity, and reliability of the research instruments, a pilot test was conducted at Francisco L. Adlaon High School and Vallehermoso High School. One

public high school in Carmen was excluded due to the absence of a Grade 12 program. Participants from the pilot test were not included in the final data collection, and necessary adjustments were made based on the pilot results. The actual study involved Grade 12 students from six public secondary schools in Carmen: Pedro S. Budiongan High School, Katipunan National High School, Isabel Gujol High School, Francisco L. Adlaon High School, Policronio S. Dano Sr. High School, and Vallehermoso High School. A two-stage sampling method was employed, first by randomly selecting schools for the pilot test and the actual study, followed by the random selection of student respondents within these schools. A total of 326 respondents participated in the study. Before data collection, informed consent was obtained from each participant, and they were provided with a brief explanation of the study's purpose and the type of questionnaires they would complete. To maintain anonymity and confidentiality, responses were coded, and personal information was kept strictly confidential.

Research Instrument

The researcher made use of a survey questionnaire as the main instrument in data gathering. The questionnaire was composed of two parts.

Part 1 focused on the level of the respondents' academic self-concept, categorized into academic effort and academic self-confidence. This section was developed by the researcher based on the Rasch analysis of the Academic Self-Concept Questionnaire utilized in the study by Joyce and Yates (2007). Since the study was conducted on foreign students, some parts of the questions were revised and adjusted to fit this research respondent and the Philippine educational setting. It was checked and reviewed by three experts in the field and was pilot-tested to test the clarity, validity, and reliability of the study tools. The needed corrections were done before it was distributed to the main respondents of this study.

In evaluating the academic self-concept in terms of academic self-effort of students, the following five orderable gradations with their respective range of means, levels, and interpretations were used.

Range of Means	Interpretation	Description
4.21 – 5.00	Very high level	very highly observed
3.41 – 4.20	High level	highly observed
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate level	moderately observed
1.81 – 2.60	Low level	less observed
1.0 – 1.80	Very Low level	not observed

For the academic self-concept in terms of academic self-confidence, the following scale was used:

Range of Means	Interpretation	Description
4.21 – 5.00	Very high level	very highly observed

3.41 – 4.20	High level	highly observed
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate level	moderately observed
1.81 – 2.60	Low level	less observed
1.0 – 1.80	Very Low level	not observed

Part 2 evaluated the respondents' level of learning outcomes in terms of the following Multiple intelligences domains: naturalistic, musical, logical, existential, interpersonal, kinesthetic, verbal, intrapersonal, and visual.

Range of Means	Interpretation	Description
8.01-10.00	Very high level	very highly observed
6.01-8.00	High level	highly observed
4.01-6.00	Moderate level	moderately observed
2.01-4.00	Low level	less observed
0-2.00	Very Low level	not observed

Statistical Treatment

The researcher used the following statistical tools in analyzing the data:

To determine the level of academic self-concept of the students in terms of their academic effort and academic confidence, a weighted mean was used with the formula:

$$\text{Weighted Mean (WM)} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

where:

WM = weighted mean

\sum = summation

f = frequency

x = weight assigned to each scale

N = number of respondents

The same statistical treatment was also used to determine the level of students' learning outcomes in terms of the following domains: Naturalistic, musical, logical, existential, interpersonal, kinesthetic, verbal, intrapersonal, and verbal.

To see if there was a significant relationship between the level of academic self-concept and the level of learning outcomes of the students, Pearson-r was utilized with the formula:

$$r = \frac{N\sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[N\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][N\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

where:

N = number of pairs of scores

$$\begin{aligned} \sum xy &= \text{sum of the products of paired scores} \\ \sum x &= \text{sum of x scores} \\ \sum y &= \text{sum of y scores} \\ \sum x^2 &= \text{sum of squared x scores} \\ \sum y^2 &= \text{sum of squared of y scores} \end{aligned}$$

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis was also used to determine the causal relationship between the academic self-concept and learning outcomes of students with the formula:

$$Y = mx_1 + mx_2 + mx_3 + b$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} Y &= \text{the dependent variable of the regression} \\ M &= \text{slope of the regression} \\ x_1 &= \text{first individual variable of the regression} \\ \text{the } x_2 &= \text{second individual variable of the regression} \\ \text{the } x_3 &= \text{third independent variable of the regression} \\ B &= \text{constant} \end{aligned}$$

Research Procedure

The data collection process followed a structured approach to ensure proper authorization and systematic administration. Initially, the researcher sought approval from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Bohol through formal written communication to conduct the study in all public secondary schools within the district of Carmen. Upon receiving approval, the researcher prepared another letter, attaching the superintendent's endorsement, which was addressed to the school administrators of the six selected schools. This letter formally requested permission to distribute the survey questionnaires to the respondents. Additionally, the researcher assured the respondents of the confidentiality of their responses to encourage honest and objective answers.

The researcher personally administered the survey questionnaires to the respondents, ensuring clarity in instructions and addressing any concerns they may have had. Once the questionnaires were completed and retrieved, the data were carefully tallied, tabulated, and analyzed. The results were then interpreted in alignment with the objectives of the study.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of the data collected from 326 public secondary school students in the 3rd District of Bohol. The respondents were from the following schools: Pedro S. Budiongan High School, Katipunan National High School, Isabel Gujol High School, Francisco L. Adlaon High School, Policronio S. Dano Sr. High School, Vallehermoso High School, Valeriano Ganas High School, Ponciano F. Ramasola High School, and Ambassador Pablo S. Suarez High School.

The first section of this chapter examines the respondents' level of academic self-concept, focusing on two key dimensions: academic effort and academic confidence. The second section discusses the respondents' level of learning outcomes across various domains, including naturalistic, musical, logical, existential, interpersonal, kinesthetic, verbal, intrapersonal, and visual intelligence. The final section explores the relationship between academic self-concept and learning outcomes, determining whether academic self-concept serves as a predictor of the different domains of learning.

Table 1.1
Level of Academic Self-Concept in Terms of Academic Effort
N = 326

Items	WM	Interpretation
1. I involve actively in community activities sponsored by the school like tree planting/clean-up drives.	3.63	High level
2. I ask my teachers regarding the lesson which I cannot understand.	3.67	High level
3. I participate actively in classroom activities.	4.22	Very high level
4. I listen intently to the teacher during lessons.	4.12	High level
5. I study hard to prepare for the tests.	3.89	High level
6. I showcase interest in school activities like joining clubs and organizations.	3.63	High level
7. I exert my best effort to pass all the subjects.	4.29	Very high level
8. I manifest a willingness to put in more effort in extra-curricular activities.	3.97	High level
9. I manage my time properly in doing school works.	3.89	High level
10. I submit my school work and projects on or before the deadlines.	3.98	High level
11. I am excited about learning new things in class.	4.14	High level
12. I collaborate in every class activity.	3.95	High level
13. I give suggestions to the class if needed.	3.58	High level
14. I volunteer to help with school activities.	3.68	High level
15. I take an active role in school works.	3.74	High level
16. I try to reflect and connect every lesson to real-life applicability.	3.72	High level
17. I relate classroom discussions with my own experiences.	3.71	High level
18. I am looking for other concept examples on my own aside from those given by the teachers to understand better.	3.74	High level

General Weighted Mean	3.86	High level
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Legend:

Range of Means	Interpretation	Description
4.21 – 5.00	very high level	very highly observed
3.41 – 4.20	high level	highly observed
2.61 – 3.40	moderate level	moderately observed
1.81 – 2.60	low level	less observed
1.00 – 1.80	very low level	not observed

The results in Table 1.1 indicate a high level of academic self-concept in terms of academic effort, with a general weighted mean of 3.86. The highest-rated item, "I exert my best effort to pass all the subjects" (WM = 4.29, Very High Level), suggests that students are highly committed to their academic success. Similarly, "I participate actively in classroom activities" (WM = 4.22, Very High Level) highlights strong classroom engagement.

Conversely, the lowest-rated item, "I give suggestions to the class if needed" (WM = 3.58, High Level), suggests that while students actively participate, they may be less inclined to voice their ideas during discussions. Despite this, the overall high level of academic effort reflects students' strong motivation and commitment to their studies.

Table 1.2
Level of Academic Self-Concept in Terms of Academic Confidence
N = 326

	Items	Level of Academic Effort	
		WM	Interpretation
1	I engage in worthwhile and sensible academic debates with peers.	3.43	High level
2	I give my best work even when under pressure	3.50	High level
3	I adopt study techniques and strategies for my learning style.	3.92	High level
4	I'd be determined to finish my studies even when challenged with difficulties.	4.10	High level
5	I exhibit good judgment about others and hence have the ability to assign appropriate tasks when in group work.	3.82	High level
6	I make myself believe that I can overcome whatever challenges I may face in school.	4.26	Very high level
7	I'd be self-reliant in completing tasks given by my teachers.	4.14	High level
8	I accept whatever feedback is in every assessment.	4.15	High level
9	I pass all subjects with self-trust and conviction.	4.20	High level
10	I absorb what is being taught in class.	3.89	High level
11	I figure out the answer to the problem asked by teachers if I try hard enough.	3.80	High level

12	I'd be adaptive to whatever skill is needed to complete a task.	3.94	High level
13	I find solutions to problems, even if it is harder than I thought.	4.05	High level
14	I'd be flexible in every situation I am in.	4.02	High level
15	I tap for assistance or help from my teacher when needed.	3.81	High level
16	I do my best, whatever the situation.	4.42	Very high level
17	I learn, even if I am nervous.	4.26	Very High level
18	I still participate in class, even in an embarrassing situation.	4.07	High level
19	I trust myself in everything I do.	4.44	Very high level
	Weighted Mean	4.01	High level

Legend:

Range of Means	Interpretation	Description
4.21 – 5.00	very high level	very highly observed
3.41 – 4.20	high level	highly observed
2.61 – 3.40	moderate level	moderately observed
1.81 – 2.60	low level	less observed
1.00 – 1.80	very low level	not observed

The results in Table 1.2 indicate a high level of academic self-concept in terms of academic confidence, with a general weighted mean of 4.01. The highest-rated item, "I trust myself in everything I do" (WM = 4.44, Very High Level), suggests that students have strong self-confidence in their academic abilities. Similarly, "I do my best, whatever the situation" (WM = 4.42, Very High Level) reflects their determination and resilience in facing academic challenges.

On the other hand, the lowest-rated item, "I engage in worthwhile and sensible academic debates with peers" (WM = 3.43, High Level), suggests that while students have confidence in their abilities, they may be less inclined to participate in academic debates. Despite this, the overall high level of academic confidence indicates that students believe in their capacity to learn, adapt, and succeed in their studies.

Table 2
Level of Learning Outcomes in the Domains
N = 326

Domains of Learning Outcomes	Mean	Interpretation
Naturalistic	5.79	Moderate level
Musical	5.53	Moderate level
Logical	5.15	Moderate level
Existential	6.55	High level
Interpersonal	5.47	Moderate level
Kinesthetic	5.94	Moderate level
Verbal	5.00	Moderate level
Intrapersonal	6.41	High level

Visual	5.35	Moderate level
	5.68	Moderate level

Legend:

Range of Means	Interpretation	Description
4.21 – 5.00	very high level	very highly observed
3.41 – 4.20	high level	highly observed
2.61 – 3.40	moderate level	moderately observed
1.81 – 2.60	low level	less observed
1.00 – 1.80	very low level	not observed

The results in Table 2 indicate a moderate overall level of learning outcomes, with a general mean of 5.68. The highest-rated domain, Existential (Mean = 6.55, High Level), suggests that students have a strong ability to reflect on deeper life questions and concepts. Similarly, the Intrapersonal domain (Mean = 6.41, High Level) indicates that students demonstrate self-awareness and an understanding of their own thoughts and emotions.

Conversely, the lowest-rated domain, Verbal (Mean = 5.00, Moderate Level), suggests that students may have moderate proficiency in language-related skills such as communication and expression. Despite this, the overall moderate level of learning outcomes indicates that students exhibit balanced development across various domains, with stronger tendencies toward self-reflection and existential thinking.

Table 3
The significant relationship between the Academic Self-Concept to each of the domains of the Learning Outcomes

Variable	Computed r	Computed t	Degrees of freedom	Tabulated t $\alpha = 0.05$	Null Hypothesis	Interpretation
Academic Self-Concept						
Naturalistic	0.145	2.634	324	1.97	Rejected	Significant
Musical	0.088	1.590			Accepted	Not Significant
Logical	0.153	2.794			Rejected	Significant
Existential	0.190	3.489			Rejected	Significant
Interpersonal	0.116	2.108			Rejected	Significant
Kinesthetic	0.149	2.708			Rejected	Significant
Verbal	0.107	1.932			Accepted	Not Significant
Intrapersonal	0.117	2.118			Rejected	Significant
Visual	0.124	2.248			Rejected	Significant

The results in Table 3 indicate the significant relationship between academic self-concept and the different domains of learning outcomes. At a 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected for most domains, indicating a significant relationship. The strongest correlation was observed in the existential domain ($r = 0.190$, $t = 3.489$, Rejected, Significant), suggesting that students with higher academic self-concept tend to have a stronger ability to reflect on deeper life concepts. Similarly, significant relationships were found in the naturalistic, logical, interpersonal, kinesthetic,

intrapersonal, and visual domains, implying that academic self-concept influences various aspects of learning.

Conversely, the null hypothesis was accepted for the musical domain ($r = 0.088$, $t = 1.590$, Not Significant) and the verbal domain ($r = 0.107$, $t = 1.932$, Not Significant), indicating that academic self-concept does not have a significant impact on these learning areas. Overall, these findings suggest that while academic self-concept plays a crucial role in most learning domains, its influence is less pronounced in musical and verbal intelligence.

According to Kumar et al. (2021), academic performance refers to the measured ability and level of achievement demonstrated by a learner in a particular subject, skill, or overall school performance. It encompasses a learner's scholastic ability and attainment, which are often assessed through tests, exams, coursework, and assignments. The measurement of academic performance is based on expected learning outcomes.

Wu et al. (2021) found a strong positive relationship between academic self-concept and academic achievement, suggesting that students with a more developed academic self-concept tend to perform better academically. This finding aligns with the studies of Olatunde (2010) and Caplin (1969), both of which revealed a significant positive relationship between self-concept and academic achievement. Similarly, Kumar (2001) identified a moderate positive correlation between academic performance and the academic achievement of distance learners.

Further supporting these findings, the study by Yazon (2015) indicated a low positive correlation between students' academic confidence and academic achievement. Their study concluded that individuals with high academic confidence and effort are generally expected to perform well academically, while those with lower confidence may struggle to achieve their full potential.

Table 4
Academic Self-Concept as a Predictor of the Domains of Learning Outcomes
N = 326

Variables	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F	Interpretation
Regression	9	6.389	0.710	1.627	0.107	Not significant
Residual	316	137.905	0.436			
Total	325	144.294				

Table 4 presents the analysis of whether the respondents' academic self-concept predicts their learning outcomes.

The findings indicate that academic self-concept (effort and confidence) does not significantly predict learning outcomes. As shown in Table 3, while some domains of learning outcomes demonstrated a significant relationship with academic self-concept, others showed no correlation. Specifically, six domains exhibited significant relationships,

whereas two domains did not. The high mean scores in the two domains were counterbalanced by lower scores in the other six, leading to the overall non-significant result in this table.

These findings contradict the assertion of Bong and Skaalvik (2003), who stated that academic self-concept influences not only students' academic performance but also their effort, engagement, persistence in classroom activities, intrinsic motivation, help-seeking behavior, and course selection. Their claims were further supported by Guo et al. (2022) in their study *Academic Self-Concept, Perceptions of the Learning Environment, Engagement, and Learning Outcomes of University Students: Relationship and Causal Ordering*, which found that academic self-concept directly predicts academic achievement.

Additionally, Trautwein et al. (2006) explored the role of self-concept and found that it reflects how individuals perceive themselves and significantly influences how they learn and perform academically. Their study emphasized that success and failure in academic settings largely depend on one's belief in their abilities and their perception of their own strengths, capabilities, and potential.

Findings

Based on the analysis of the data, the following findings came up:

1. The students' academic self-concept levels in terms of academic effort and academic confidence are both high.
2. The students' learning outcomes in the existential and intrapersonal domains were high, while moderate in the naturalistic, musical, logical, interpersonal, kinesthetic, verbal, and visual domains.
3. There is a significant relationship between the level of academic self-concept of the respondents to the naturalistic, logical, existential, interpersonal, kinesthetic, intrapersonal, and visual domains of the learning outcomes but revealed no relationship between the respondents' academic self-concept to their musical and verbal domains of learning outcomes. Hence, the naturalistic, logical, existential, interpersonal, kinesthetic, intrapersonal, and visual domains of the learning outcomes are influenced by the respondents' academic self-concept while their musical and verbal domains of learning outcomes are not influenced by their academic self-concept.
4. The respondents' academic self-concept is not a predictor of their level of learning outcomes.

Conclusions

The student's academic self-concept is not a significant predictor of their learning outcomes. Someone with a high academic self-concept is not expected to attain well in their learning outcomes or the other way around. It further entailed that the academic self-concept was not a significant factor to consider when measuring the musical and verbal learning outcomes of the students but was considered a significant factor when

measuring the naturalistic, logical, existential, interpersonal, kinesthetic, intrapersonal, and visual learning outcomes of the students.

Recommendations

In view of the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The guidance counselor may offer academic confidence and effort enhancement programs to sustain students' self-concept in general. These would allow the students to examine their thoughts, feelings, and abilities as individuals and be more positive about themselves.
2. The guidance counselor may implement the psycho-educational program in the formal and informal curriculum for parents and teachers to provide a chance for students to express themselves and develop their self-esteem and self-confidence.
3. Teachers should provide situations of success for all students; this will improve students' sense of confidence, with all the benefits that could arise from such a case which might include perseverance to strive harder in their studies.
3. In order to improve self-concept among the students, more opportunities for participation in academic activities may be provided by the teachers during workshop sessions which in turn may be helpful in increasing the students' academic self-concept.
4. Students may involve themselves in various activities that would further enhance their level of confidence. Going the extra mile is suggested for them to acquire a better level of learning outcomes and academic achievement.
5. Parents are advised to guide their children properly and provide the love and support they deserve so that their academic confidence and effort will be reinforced. Consequently, the student's academic achievement will be improved.
6. The Guidance counselor may provide counseling sessions for students with low academic self-concept so that they may improve their academic position as well.
7. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct a study on the factors affecting one's level of academic confidence and academic efforts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to the highest ethical standards to ensure the integrity, confidentiality, and well-being of the participants. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring that they fully understood the purpose of the study, their rights, and the voluntary nature of their participation. In the case of minor participants, parental or guardian consent was also secured.

Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained by assigning unique codes to participants instead of using their real names. All collected data was stored securely and accessed only by authorized researchers. The study complied with the ethical guidelines of the institution and relevant research ethics committees, ensuring that participants did not face any harm, discomfort, or undue pressure to participate.

Furthermore, participants had the right to withdraw from the study at any stage without any consequences. The research also ensured that no coercion was applied, and no personal or sensitive information was disclosed. Ethical approval was sought from the relevant authorities before conducting the study. The findings were reported honestly and objectively, with due acknowledgment of sources and without any form of data manipulation or fabrication.

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